

These are what seen fractals look like figuratively:

·FLUME·

WOODS

Once again, these images shown above are what seen fractals are figuratively and what seen fractals mean figuratively, and these seen fractals shown above are always in motion and are the size of tree branches, bush branches, flowers, leaves and grass.

This set is timed as 7:58, and is dated as the 9th day of the 2nd month, of the 2025th year.